

A novel one-pot synthesis of 3,3-diaryloxindoles

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Abstract : Treatment of *N*-substituted isatins with various Grignard reagents gave 3,3-diaryloxindoles in good yield. The formation of 3,3-diaryloxindoles involves an unstable diol intermediate which undergoes rearrangement in the presence of an acid generated *in situ*.

Keywords : Isatin, Grignard addition, oxindoles, pinacolone rearrangement.

Introduction

The oxindole ring is a prominent structural motif found in numerous natural products and pharmaceutically active compounds¹. The existing methods for oxindole synthesis are limited in their scope and generality. Among the techniques commonly used in synthesis are derivatization from other heterocyclic compounds (e.g. Wolf-Kishner reduction of the corresponding isatin, oxidation of the corresponding indole²), cyclization of *o*-aminophenylacetic acid derivatives² and radical cyclization reaction³. The intermolecular Heck reaction can be used to generate oxidindoles⁴, and asymmetric cyclizations have found widespread use in the synthesis. Alternatively, the intermolecular arylation of amides⁵ or amide enolate^{1,6} has been employed to access oxindoles. Unfortunately, all of the aforementioned methods inherently require a specifically functionalized precursor (e.g. the presence of an *ortho*-halogen, an amino group). A classical approach to the oxindole system that circumvents the need for such functionalization is the Friedel-Crafts cyclization onto α -halo⁷ or α -hydroxy⁸ acetanilides. While it is a modular technique in that the reactive functional group is transferred away from the aromatic nucleus, the strongly acidic conditions and high temperatures required for such reactions limit the range of functional groups that are tolerated⁹. A conceptually new synthesis has been reported by Fujita *et al.*¹⁰, where a rhodium-catalysed lactamization of amino alcohol has been developed to

give oxindoles in good yields.

In continuation of our work¹¹ in synthesizing polycyclic compounds through dianionic-oxy-Cope rearrangement, we herein report an easy route to the synthesis of 3,3-diaryloxindoles from *N*-substituted isatins.

Results and discussion

Initially we have made an attempt to synthesize various 2,3-diols of isatin derivatives which serve as precursor to carry out dianionic-oxy-Cope rearrangement and an acid-catalysed rearrangement (pinacolone rearrangement) but later we found that these diols are highly unstable and undergo rearrangement in the presence of an acid, generated *in situ* from an ammonium chloride/water¹² mixture to give a 3,3-diaryloxindoles (as shown in Schemes 1 and 2) in good yields.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Although we did not add hydrolytic agent at any stage of the reaction, we strongly believe that the acid is generated *in situ* as the reaction was quenched with excess of saturated solution of ammonium chloride. Being a salt derived from a strong acid and a weak base, its hydrolysis in aqueous medium generates H^+ ions¹² (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. General mechanism of the formation of products.

Identical results were obtained in other cases. All the products exhibited satisfactory elemental analysis. Finally the structure was further confirmed by single crystal X-ray analysis of 3a and 3b¹³. The reaction time and yield of the products are given in Table 1.

Entry	Product	R	R ¹	Stirring (under N ₂ atm.)		Yield (%)
				0 °C (h)	RT (h)	
1	3a	H	H	1	5	74
2	3b	CH ₃	H	1	5	82
3	3c	H	CH ₃	1	5	76
4	3d	OCH ₃	H	1	5	75
5	3e	-	-	1	5	72
6	5a	H	H	1	5	68
7	5b	CH ₃	H	1	5	73
8	5c	-	-	1	5	70

RT = Room temperature.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by TLC on silica gel. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 8300 series FT-IR spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ using TMS as an internal standard on a Bruker 300 spectrometer at 300 MHz. ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker 300 spectrometer at 75 MHz. Mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol DX 303 HF spectrometer. Elemental analysis was carried out on Perkin-Elmer 2400 B instrument.

General procedure for the synthesis of 3,3-diarlyloxindole derivatives (3a-e and 5a-c) :

To a solution of arylmagnesium bromide in dry THF at 0 °C under N₂ atm. [prepared from Mg (0.03 mol) and bromobenzene/substituted bromobenzene/bromonaphthalene (0.03 mol)], *N*-substituted isatin (5 mmol) in dry THF was added dropwise. After the addition, the mixture was stirred at 0 °C (under N₂ atm.) for 1 h, and then it was stirred at room temperature (under N₂ atm.) for 5 h. After the completion of the reaction as evidenced by TLC, it was quenched with a saturated solution of NH₄Cl (100 ml). The product was extracted into diethyl ether (100 ml), washed with water followed by brine and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and evaporated. Purification of the residue by column chromatography on silica gel (100–200 mesh) using hexane-ethyl acetate (5%) as eluent affords the corresponding compound.

The compound 3a was prepared by the addition of *N*-

allylisatin (**1**) to 6 equiv. of phenylmagnesium bromide in dry THF. The *N*-substituted isatin in dry THF was added slowly, over the period of half an hour to a grey cloudy white solution of phenylmagnesium bromide.

The compound **3a** was obtained as pale-yellow solid (m.p. 120–125 °C). The ¹H NMR spectrum of the compound **3a** showed peak at δ 4.41–5.90 for the allylic protons and at δ 6.90–7.30 for the aromatic ring protons. The ¹³C NMR spectrum of compound **3a** showed peak at δ 45.56 for the allylic carbon attached to the nitrogen, at δ 62.66 for the quaternary carbon (adjacent to oxindole carbon) and showed peak at δ 177.41 for the oxindole carbon. The mass spectrum of **3a** showed peak at *m/z* 325 (M⁺). Similar procedure was followed for the other products **3(b-c)** and **5(a-c)**.

The compound **3b** was obtained as an apple-green solid (m.p. 110–115 °C). The ¹H NMR spectra of compound **3b** showed peak at δ 2.16 as a singlet for the methyl protons (6H, CH₃), at δ 4.39–5.85 for the allylic protons and at δ 6.74–7.15 for the aromatic ring protons. The ¹³C NMR spectra of compound **3b** showed peak at δ 21.11 for the methyl carbon directly attached to the aromatic ring, at δ 42.56 for the allylic carbon attached to the nitrogen, at δ 61.97 for the quaternary carbon (adjacent to oxindole carbon) and showed peak at δ 177.59 for the oxindole carbon. The mass spectrum of **3b** showed peak at *m/z* 353 (M⁺).

The compound **5c** was obtained as a light-brown fluffy solid (m.p. 75–80 °C). The ¹H NMR spectra of compound **5c** showed peak at δ 5.26 as a singlet for the benzylic hydrogen and showed a multiplet at δ 6.78–8.18 for the aromatic ring protons. The ¹³C NMR spectra of compound **5c** showed peak at δ 76.08 for the quaternary carbon and at δ 176.22 for the oxindole carbon. The mass spectrum **5c** showed *m/z* at 475 (M⁺).

1-Allyl-3,3-diphenylindolin-2-one (3a) :

Yield 74%, m.p. 120–125 °C (Found : C, 84.97; H, 6.02; N, 4.19. Calcd. for C₂₃H₁₉NO : C, 84.89; H, 5.88; N, 4.30%); IR (KBr) : 1708.8 cm⁻¹ (C=O); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃/300 MHz) δ : 4.42 (2H, d, *J* 3.6 Hz, NCH₂), 5.17–5.22 (2H, d, allylic), 5.83–5.90 (1H, m, allylic), 6.91 (1H, d, *J* 6 Hz, ArH), 7.05–7.09 (1H, m, ArH), 7.25–7.30 (12H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃/75 MHz) δ : 177.41, 142.37, 142.17, 133.02, 131.59, 128.65,

128.60, 128.37, 127.48, 126.29, 122.99, 117.67, 62.66, 42.73 ppm; EIMS *m/z* : 325 (M⁺).

1-Allyl-3,3-di-p-tolyindolin-2-one (3b) :

Yield 82%, m.p. 110–115 °C (Found : C, 84.85; H, 6.46; N, 4.04. Calcd. for C₂₅H₂₃NO : C, 84.95; H, 6.55; N, 3.96%); IR (KBr) : 1712.7 cm⁻¹ (C=O); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃/300 MHz) δ : 2.16 (6H, s, ArCH₃), 4.27 (2H, m, NCH₂) 5.05 (2H, d, *J* 13.2 Hz, allylic), 5.67–5.76 (1H, m, allylic), 6.74–7.15 (12H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃/75 MHz) δ : 177.59, 142.30, 139.27, 136.98, 133.40, 131.51, 129.24, 128.38, 128.13, 126.07, 122.84, 117.45, 61.97, 42.56, 21.11 ppm; EIMS *m/z* : 353 (M⁺).

1-Allyl-3,3-di-o-tolyindolin-2-one (3c) :

Yield 76%, m.p. 128–130 °C (Found : C, 84.05; H, 6.69; N, 3.84. Calcd. for C₂₅H₂₃NO : C, 84.95; H, 6.55; N, 3.96%); IR (KBr) : 1703.0 cm⁻¹ (C=O); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃/300 MHz) δ : 1.85 (6H, s, ArCH₃), 4.41–4.43 (2H, m, NCH₂), 5.30 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz, allylic), 5.39 (1H, d, *J* 12.8 Hz, allylic), 5.84–5.94 (1H, m, allylic), 6.92–7.98 (12H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃/75 MHz) δ : 176.86, 143.39, 137.86, 134.65, 131.59, 131.08, 130.42, 130.01, 128.43, 126.25, 126.19, 125.06, 123.65, 118.79, 62.01, 42.87, 19.66 ppm; EIMS *m/z* : 353 (M⁺).

1-Allyl-3,3-di-p-anisylindolin-2-one (3d) :

Yield 75%, m.p. 118–120 °C (Found : C, 77.76; H, 6.23; N, 3.72. Calcd. for C₂₅H₂₃NO₃ : C, 77.90; H, 6.01; N, 3.63%); IR (KBr) : 1710.6 cm⁻¹ (C=O); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃/300 MHz) δ : 3.70 (6H, s, OCH₃), 4.25 (2H, m, NCH₂), 5.09 (2H, d, *J* 13.0 Hz, allylic), 5.65–5.74 (1H, m, allylic), 6.60–7.82 (12H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃/75 MHz) δ : 177.58, 142.24, 139.20, 137.02, 133.32, 131.46, 129.28, 131.46, 129.28, 128.34, 128.24, 126.22, 122.78, 116.42, 56.68, 42.60, 19.66 ppm; EIMS *m/z* : 385 (M⁺).

1-Allyl-3,3-dinaphthalen-1-yl indolin-2-one (3e) :

Yield 72%, m.p. 135–140 °C (Found : C, 87.64; H, 5.36; N, 3.40. Calcd. for C₃₁H₂₃NO : C, 87.50; H, 5.44; N, 3.29%); IR (KBr) : 1706.9 cm⁻¹ (C=O); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃/300 MHz) δ : 4.37 (1H, dd, *J* 16, 5.1 Hz, NCH₂), 4.54 (1H, dd, *J* 16, 5.1 Hz, NCH₂), 5.32 (1H, d, *J* 10.2 Hz, allylic), 5.40 (1H, d, *J* 10.2 Hz, allylic), 6.91–7.89 (18H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃/75 MHz) δ : 177.20, 142.59, 135.15, 134.37, 131.74, 131.03, 130.25, 129.95,

129.61, 129.09, 126.19, 125.55, 125.05, 125.01, 124.76, 124.57, 123.51, 118.51, 78.63, 42.75 ppm; EIMS m/z : 425 (M^+).

1-Benzyl-3,3-diphenylindolin-2-one (5a) :

Yield 68%, m.p. 143–145 °C (Found : C, 86.25; H, 5.74; N, 3.89. Calcd. for $C_{27}H_{21}NO$: C, 86.37; H, 5.63; N, 3.73%); IR (KBr) : 1699.2 cm^{-1} (C=O); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3/300$ MHz) δ : 4.78 (1H, d, J 16 Hz, NCH_2), 5.02 (1H, d, J 16 Hz, NCH_2), 6.75–7.41 (19H, m, ArH); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3/75$ MHz) δ : 175.85, 140.72, 138.33, 133.54, 129.88, 127.84, 126.99, 126.75, 126.40, 125.89, 125.41, 123.47, 123.12, 121.69, 76.15, 42.16 ppm; EIMS m/z : 375 (M^+).

1-Benzyl-3,3-di-p-tolylindolin-2-one (5b) :

Yield 73%, m.p. 125–127 °C (Found : C, 86.47; H, 6.11; N, 3.59. Calcd. for $C_{29}H_{25}NO$: C, 86.31; H, 6.24; N, 3.47%); IR (KBr) : 1704.6 cm^{-1} (C=O); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3/300$ MHz) δ : 2.02 (6H, s, CH_3), 5.22 (2H, s, NCH_2), 6.74–7.40 (17H, m, ArH); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3/75$ MHz) δ : 175.96, 143.40, 141.52, 135.88, 134.66, 129.42, 128.46, 127.57, 126.82, 126.80, 126.53, 125.89, 125.41, 123.54, 123.06, 120.52, 76.16, 44.48, 20.22 ppm; EIMS m/z : 403 (M^+).

1-Benzyl-3,3-dinaphthalen-1-yl indolin-2-one (5c) :

Yield 70%, m.p. 75–80 °C (Found : C, 88.45, H, 5.20; N, 3.09. Calcd. for $C_{35}H_{25}NO$: C, 88.39; H, 5.29; N, 2.94%); IR (KBr) : 1706.3 cm^{-1} (C=O); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3/300$ MHz) δ : 5.26 (2H, s, NCH_2), 4.79 (2H, d, J 5.5 Hz, ArH), 7.23–8.18 (21H, m, ArH); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3/75$ MHz) δ : 176.22, 143.38, 141.66, 134.81, 133.46, 132.58, 128.61, 128.52, 127.00, 126.81, 126.40, 125.76, 125.58, 124.34, 122.22, 121.82, 76.08, 42.02 ppm; EIMS m/z : 475 (M^+).

In conclusion our work reports an easy route to the synthesis of functionalized 3,3-diaryloxindole analogues in a single step.

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